

EFFECTS OF PLASMA NITRIDING AND DUPLEX TREATMENTS ON THE CORROSION RESISTANCE OF UNS S32760 STAINLESS STEEL

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ABSTRACT

UNS S32760 super duplex stainless steel has excellent corrosion resistance and mechanical properties that are superior to those exhibited by austenitic and ferritic stainless steels, but which can still be improved by surface treatments. However, due attention should be paid to the corrosion resistance properties. Thus, the aim of this work is to investigate the effect of plasma nitriding and the duplex treatment on the corrosion resistance of UNS S32760 steel. A conventional plasma nitriding treatment lasting 4 and two duplex treatments were studied, which repeated the nitriding and then subjected to the deposition of titanium nitride films for 2 h and 4h using the cathode cage plasma deposition technique. The temperature used in all treatments was 723 k. The samples were evaluated by Optical Microscopy, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) maps, X-ray Diffraction with routine application of Rietveld, Vickers Microhardness and Rockwell indentation adhesion test. The sample subjected only to nitriding treatment presented the highest surface hardness, 4.06 times higher than that presented by the base material. In the samples submitted to the duplex treatment the presence of stoichiometric titanium was observed on the nitride layer. The corrosion tests revealed on sample NC4 evidenced the positive effect of plasma nitriding on corrosion resistance.

KEYWORDS: Plasma Nitriding, Duplex Treatment, Titanium Nitride, Cathodic Cage, Corrosion Resistance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Super duplex stainless steels (SDSS) are known for their excellent pitting and general corrosion resistance and are characterized by their microstructure, consisting of grains of ferrite and austenite with similar volume fraction, which gives them mechanical properties superior to ferritic and austenitic stainless steels [1]. In addition, they have adequate weldability and relatively low cost. SDSS are mainly used on oil and gas platforms, in components such as valves, pipes, and flanges [2], [3]. Despite their good mechanical properties, superior to those presented by common duplex steels, the tribological

properties still need to be improved. In this context, thermochemical treatments with coating deposition processes, such as plasma nitriding and Physical Vapor Deposition (PVD), appear as alternatives to improved mechanical surface properties of metallic materials [4]. It is known, however, that heating super duplex stainless steels may result in the degradation of the others properties, especially toughness and corrosion resistance [1], [5]. Thus, besides studying the effect of the treatments on their tribological properties, it is also necessary to track the evolution of corrosion resistance.

Among PVD techniques, the Cathodic Cage Plasma Deposition (CCPD), enables the deposition of coatings with customizable compositions as a result of the reaction of elements removed by sputtering from the cage (target) which combine with reactive plasma gases in the reactor and are deposited on the surface of the samples. Thus, the selection of cage material and the gases used need to be chosen according to the expected composition of the coatings. To deposit titanium nitride (TiN) films, for example, a titanium cage and a mixture of nitrogen and inert gases need to be used [6]–[8].

A key point to the efficiency of coatings for tribological applications is adhesion, which controls delamination of the coating. If it occurs, the delamination contributes to accelerating the abrasive wear process by adding the wear debris as a large number of abrasive particles [9]. Thus, the deposition of these coatings is usually preceded by a conventional nitriding treatment which, by the formation of a diffusion zone, creates a hardness gradient towards the core as a consequence of the decrease in nitrogen concentration in the same direction [10]. Deposition directly onto the soft substrate is known to cause the so-called eggshell effect, since excessive deformation of the substrate contributes to the formation and propagation of cracks in the film, which results in delamination [11]–[13]. The combination of conventional nitriding and film deposition is known as “duplex treatment” [14]–[16]. An initial study, linked to this work, investigated the effects of duplex treatment in the mechanical and tribological properties of UNS S32760 and results showed improved, with a 4 times hardness increase and reduced wear volume by up to 9.41 times. [17] The objective of this work is to study the effect of the plasma nitriding and duplex treatment (plasma nitriding followed by titanium nitride deposition using the cathodic cage plasma deposition technique) in the corrosion resistance of UNS S32760 super duplex stainless steel.

The paper then presents a description of the materials used and the methods employed. The samples were evaluated by Optical Microscopy, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) maps, X-ray Diffraction with routine application of Rietveld, Vickers Microhardness and Rockwell indentation adhesion test. Then the results and a detailed discussion are presented. And then the conclusion section is presented.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

UNS S32760 super duplex stainless steel samples, with chemical composition (wt%) 25.30 Cr; 6.85 Ni, 3.70 Mo, Mn; Si < 1.00; 0.75 Cu; 0.75 W; 0.25 N; C < 0.03 C and iron in balance, were provided by the supplier. Cylindrical specimens with a diameter of 15 mm and a length of 6 mm were ground with silicon carbide papers and then polished using 1 μm diamond paste.

The effects of the treatments of plasma nitriding, schematically represented in Figure 1a, and duplex treatment (plasma nitriding followed by cathodic cage deposition using a titanium cage, Figure 1b), were studied. Before nitriding, the samples were pre-sputtered in an inert atmosphere (Ar = 50%; H₂ = 50%) for 1 h at a temperature of 623 K and pressure of 130 Pa. Then the atmosphere was adjusted to the nitriding conditions (H₂ = 80%; N₂ = 20%), and maintained for 4 h at 723 K and 200 Pa. The deposition step was also preceded by a pre-sputtering at the same conditions as applied before nitriding, and then the atmosphere was adjusted to (25% H₂ - 75% N₂), with a temperature of 723 K, pressure of 200 Pa, and two different treatment times, 2h and 4h, were used. Table 1 summarizes the nomenclature of the samples and the respective treatment conditions applied.

Table 1. Nomenclature of the base sample and the treated samples

Sample	Processing Conditions							
	Plasma Nitriding				Cathodic Cage Plasma Deposition			
	Temperature (K)	Pressure (Pa)	Time (h)	Gases (H ₂ : N ₂)	Temperature (K)	Pressure (Pa)	Time (h)	Gases (H ₂ : N ₂)
Base metal								
NC4	723	200	4	80%:20%			-	-
N4-D2	723	200	4	80%:20%	723	200	2	25%:75%
N4-D4	723	200	4	80%:20%	723	200	4	25%:75%

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the treatments of: (a) plasma nitriding (b) cathodic cage plasma deposition.

The transverse section surface of the samples was analyzed by optical microscopy (Upright BEL Photonics, MTM-1), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (FEI Quanta FEG 250) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) (Apollo X-SDD Det). The samples were etched with Behara solution to reveal the microstructure. The phases present were investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD) using a Cu-K α radiation source. The copper target tube was operated at a voltage of 40 kV, a current of 40 mA, and a scanning range of 10° to 105°. Rietveld analysis was performed using ReX Powder Diffraction Software (version 9.1). To assess corrosion behavior of the samples, potentiodynamic polarization and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) test were used. The potentiodynamic polarization measurements were carried out in a solution of 3.5% NaCl at room temperature (RT) after 3600 s stabilization of the open circuit potential (OCP) in the range from -0.2 V vs. OCP to 3 mA.cm⁻² current density. Tafel extrapolation method was used to obtain the corrosion potential E_{corr} and corrosion current density i_{corr} . For the EIS tests, the frequency range was 105 Hz to 10⁻² Hz, and the amplitude of the ac signal was 15 mV (rms) with 7 points per decade of acquisition rate. The obtained diagrams were fitted using Electric Equivalent Circuits (EECs) using the Zview® Software. Three-electrode cell comprising the all samples, with or without the different deposition conditions, as working electrode (0.2827 cm² of exposed area), an Ag/AgCl reference electrode and a platinum wire counter electrode was employed. A Potentiostat/Galvanostat/ZRA Gamry reference 600+ was used for the measurements. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to identify morphology surface samples after corrosion experiments.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Optical microscopy

Figure 2 shows the cross-sectional micrograph of the NC4 sample obtained by optical microscopy to verify the formation of the nitride layer.

The substrate microstructure is typical of duplex stainless steels and consists of a lamellar arrangement of ferrite and austenite aligned in the rolling direction [18]–[20]. It is possible to observe near the surface the formation of uniform and relatively dense layers associated with the nitriding treatment. The tendency for columnar growth in some regions of the layers, following a pattern along the ferrite and austenite, according to Tschiptschin et al. [20], is associated with the formation of expanded austenite and ferrite phases in the nitride layers. Although in this work no significant variation in layer thickness was observed in the regions corresponding to the ferrite grains and those corresponding to austenite grains, Tschiptschin et al. [20] justified this lack of difference in the growth rate by the compensatory effect of nitrogen diffusion coefficients in the BCC and FCC structures (which is faster in the former). This can be associated with a predominance of different iron and chromium nitrides formation about the formation of the diffusion structures, suggested by the columnar growth regions.

Figure 2. Transverse micrographs obtained by optical microscopy after nitriding, sample NC4

3.2. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Figure 3 shows the micrographs obtained by Scanning Electron Microscopy - SEM of the cross sections of the samples subjected to the duplex treatment, N4-D2, and N4-D4.

Figure 3. Cross-sectional micrographs obtained by SEM of the samples: (a) N4-D2 and (b) N4-D4

The result proved that the two deposition conditions resulted in the formation of a TiN film. The thickness of the deposited TiN film is observed to increase linearly with treatment time. A slight difference is observed in contrast between the outermost region of the film, named zone 2, and the innermost part named zone 1. This behavior can be related mainly to two characteristics of the process, the first is the pre-sputtering step in the deposition treatment, which can deposit only titanium taken from the cage because the inert atmosphere composed of argon and hydrogen does not react with these elements. Second, because this region is an interface region subject to the diffusion of elements between

the nitride layer and the deposited TiN film, the presence of this interaction region can contribute to improving the film's adhesion conditions, decreasing the stresses generated at the interface. [21], [22].

3.3. Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy - EDS

Figure 4 shows the chemical element distribution map (EDS/SEM) for samples N4-D4. It can be seen that the deposited film is composed only of nitrogen and titanium, due to the high concentration of these elements shown on the map. Just below, the indicated region as the nitride layer, there is a considerable concentration of nitrogen combined simultaneously with the main elements of the substrate (iron, chromium, and nickel), indicating the formation of the layer from the combination of the elements removed by sputtering of the sample surface with the nitrogen from the plasma. The lower relative amount of nitrogen, when compared to the film region, is related to the differences in the relative nitrogen concentrations for the stoichiometric compositions of the TiN, Fe₂-3N, and Fe₄N [23]–[28]. In the region below the nitride layer, it is also possible to observe a considerable concentration of nitrogen, which may be associated with the formation of the diffusion zone. The result also corroborates the discussion presented in section 3.1 for the optical microscopy results, in which the structure of the duplex steel was described as inheriting the structure of ferrite and austenite. It can be seen that the largest concentrations of chromium and nickel occur in distinct regions, right and left, respectively, which can be associated with the preexisting ferrite and austenite grains, since chromium partitions to ferrite and nickel partitions to austenite.

Figure 4. Chemical element concentration maps obtained by EDS for sample N4-D4.

3.4. X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

Figure 5 presents the XRD patterns presented by the base sample and the treated samples, along with the corresponding predicted spectra. The substrate sample, Figure 5a, consists of a combination of four phases with the following volume fractions: 19.4% alpha iron (Fe), 3.3% iron-nickel (Fe_{0.96}Ni_{0.05}), 68.4% iron-chromium (Fe_{0.97}Cr_{0.03}) and 8.9% chromium (Cr). The Cards no. 64795 [29], 103562 [30], 625871[31] and, 41505 [32], published and available in the Inorganic Crystal Structure Database

(ICSD) were used for modeling the theoretical Rietveld profile, in red. The Rwp and GOF parameter values obtained after Rietveld refinement agrees with the described phases [33], [34].

Figure 5. X-ray diffraction pattern of the samples: (a) Base metal; (b) NC4; (c) N4-D2; (d) N4-D4.

Figure 5b shows the patterns referring to sample NC4, submitted only to the conventional nitriding treatment. Seven distinct phases were identified with the following percentage values: 14.3% alpha iron (Fe), 28.0% ferrochromium (Fe_{0.97}Cr_{0.03}), 9.5% expanded austenite (FeN_{0.03}), 11.4% iron nitride (Fe₂N), 13.2% iron nitride (Fe₂₄N₁₀), 15.4% iron nitride (Fe₃N), and 8.2% chromium nitride (CrN). The respective cards no. 64795 [29] 625871 [31], 31899 [35], 24651 [36], 24652 [36], 24650 [36] and 37412 [37] from the Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD) were used for modeling the Rietveld profile.

The presence of the iron alpha (Fe) and ferrochromium (Fe_{0.97}Cr_{0.03}) phases reveals that the thickness of the nitride layer was too thin, registering the substrate phases. The expanded austenite phase (FeN_{0.03}), on the other hand, shows that the nitriding layer has an appreciable diffusion zone, which is important for improving the bonding conditions, as discussed previously [38]. The presence of the nitride layer pointed out in the optical microscopy results of section 3.1, is confirmed by the iron nitride and chromium nitride phases. Although nickel can also form a stable nitride, there is a greater tendency for iron nitrides to form and, as a consequence, the ferrite and austenite grains are enriched in nickel [5]. Chromium nitride formation is enhanced at temperatures above 673 K [39], and although the

diffusivity of all the substitutional elements increases with temperature, the bond between chromium and nitrogen is larger than that of the other substitutional elements, including nickel [40]. The combination of the depletion of chromium content and the percentage increase in nickel in the iron matrix contributes to a greater stabilization of the austenite phase, which is a reasonable explanation for the considerable contents of expanded austenite in the nitride layer and the absence of the expanded ferrite phase. In other words, the ferrite grains decompose into chromium nitride CrN and austenite.

Figures 5c and 5d correspond, respectively, to the patterns of samples N4-D2 and N4-D4 consisting of the combination of eight phases, the titanium nitride (TiN) phase, registered in the Inorganic Crystal Structure Database (ICSD) by card number 64909 [41], in addition to the seven phases presented by sample NC4. The percentages found for sample N4-D2 were as follows: 6.1% alpha iron (Fe), 25.6% ferrochromium (Fe_{0.97}Cr_{0.03}), 14.1 % expanded austenite (FeN_{0.03}), 7.9% iron nitride (Fe₂N), 5.9 % iron nitride (Fe₂₄N₁₀), 2.6 % iron nitride (Fe₃N), 10.1% chromium nitride (CrN) and 27.7% titanium nitride (TiN). N4-D4 had the following percentages: 2.5% alpha iron (Fe), 17.1% ferrochromium (Fe_{0.97}Cr_{0.03}), 7.6% expanded austenite (FeN_{0.03}), 7.0% iron nitride (Fe₂N), 6.9 % iron nitride (Fe₂₄N₁₀), 12.5 % iron nitride (Fe₃N), 12.0% chromium nitride (CrN) and 34.4% titanium nitride (TiN).

The result agrees with those presented in the EDS map of section 3.3, in which the concentrations of nitrogen and titanium in the film region already suggested the formation of titanium nitride. The higher volume fraction of titanium nitride (TiN) in sample N4-D4 corroborates with the results presented in section 3.2, which exhibited growth in the thickness of the deposited film with increasing deposition time. The values presented after deposition show no significant changes in the relative percentages of the phases associated with the nitriding layer. The Rwp and GOF parameters obtained after the Rietveld refinement and shown in Figure 5 prove the agreement between the theoretical phases and the experimental profile, ensuring the formation of a stoichiometric titanium nitride (TiN) film [33], [34].

3.5. Electrochemical Tests

Figure 6 are presented potentiodynamic polarization curves for treated and untreated samples. The cathodic slopes for untreated and treated samples are fairly similar, indicating an activation-controlled process. Furthermore, E_{corr} of the base metal has a higher value compared to all coated samples, indicating a more noble behavior. The anodic branches evidence that the coated samples with duplex treatments (N4-D2 and N4-D4) present a more active behavior with higher values of i_{corr} and limit current density, whilst the nitrided sample (NC4) has similar behavior to the base metal with a large passive range at lower current densities. The reduction in corrosion resistance can be attributed, in part, to the chromium nitride (CrN) precipitation, evidenced in the section 3.4 results, and which is associated with a loss of chromium from the substrate [42]. Besides that, CrN formation leads to decreased ϵ -nitride (Fe₂₋₃N), this latter responsible to improved corrosion resistance [42].

Figure 6. Polarization curves for untreated and treated samples in after 3600 s in 3.5 % NaCl solution.

The XRD results presented in section 3.4 showed a higher percentage of chromium nitride for the samples with duplex treatment, which can be ascribed to the additional treatment time of these samples at temperatures over 673 K, revealing a less corrosion resistant substrate due to chromium loss. This condition must weaken the protective properties of the passive layer favoring the formation of galvanic cells in which the substrate is anodically dissolved, while the coating remains unbroken [43]

Table 2 summarises the corrosion potential and current density results of the samples. The results show an increase of one order of magnitude in current density for samples submitted to duplex treatment when compared to untreated and nitride samples. This behavior may be related to the presence of PVD deposited coatings defects typical, such as pores and voids. These defects are related to pre-existing defects on the surface and decrease with the increase deposition rate [44]. The lower value observed for sample N4-D4 compared to N4-D2 shows that increasing the deposition time improves the corrosion resistance of the samples with duplex treatment, this was expected due to the increased uniformity of the films with the deposition time, section 3.2. Additionally, the longer deposition time favors a reduction in the defect density due to increased diffusion [45].

Table 2. Summarized potentiodynamic polarization results.

Condition	E_{corr} [V vs Ag/AgCl]	i_{corr} [A.cm ⁻²]
Base metal	-0.112	2.37E-07
NC4	-0.201	2.23E-07
N4-D2	-0.380	2.41E-06
N4-D4	-0.352	2.07E-06

Figure 7 shows surfaces macroscopic optical analysis before, Figures 7 a-c, and after, Figures 7 d-f, electrochemical tests. The images indicate surface generalized corrosion for NC4 condition, and pitting corrosion (or localized corrosion) for the duplex treatments, which can be seen from region pointed out by yellow arrows. This behavior shows that the coating material exhibits good corrosion resistance, however, the defects reported here act as a path for the salt solution to reach the substrate. The XRD results presented in section 3.4 showed a chromium nitride higher percentage for the samples with duplex treatment, which is due to the additional time of treatment of these samples at temperatures over 673 K and reveal a substrate less resistant to corrosion, due to the loss of chromium. These conditions favor the formation of a galvanic cell is formed in which the substrate is anodically dissolved, while the coating remains unbroken [43]

Figure 7. Macroscopic optical analysis before and after electrochemical tests: (a) NC4 before; (b) N4-D2 before; (c) N4-D4 before; (d) NC4 after; (e) N4-D2 after (f) N4-D4 after.

Figure 8 shows SEM micrographs post corrosion. In Figure 8a, region “A” do not had contact with an electrolyte (region without corrosion) and region “B” had contact with an electrolyte (region with corrosion). For the base material can be observed surface general corrosion, with a consequence of damage caused by the saline solution. This behavior is common in super duplex stainless steel because as higher as pitting resistance equivalent number (PREN>40), lower possibility localized corrosion to occur at chloride-rich environments [46] the grain boundaries corrosion also can be observed in Figure 8a. In contrast, all coated specimens show localized corrosion, with a pitting corrosion morphology at surface, corroborating with Figure 7 discussion, yellow arrows indicate the pitting corrosion regions.

Figure 8. SEM images after electrochemical tests. (a) base metal; (b) NC4; (c) N4-D2; (d) N4-D4.

3.6. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy

Figure 9 shows the Bode (Figure 9a and b) and Nyquist (Figure 9c) diagrams, for the untreated and treated UNS S32760 samples, obtained after 1h of OCP stabilization. The Bode plots (Figure 9a) show that the NC4 sample has a higher impedance modulus than the base metal in all the studied frequency range, being more evident in the medium frequency region (from 50 Hz to 5×10^3 Hz). This better performance can be attributed to the protection by the nitride layer and corroborates with the polarization curves results, where, although the nitrided sample presented lower corrosion potential than the base metal, the corrosion current decreased with nitriding and reflects a slower evolution of the corrosion process. On the other hand, the N4-D2 and N4-D4 samples showed the lowest impedance modulus in the low frequency range (between 1×10^{-2} Hz and 50 Hz) being up to an order of magnitude lower than the uncoated sample, and as shown in the potentiodynamic polarization curves, Figure 6, reflect a loss of corrosion resistance with the deposition of the TiN coating. The phase angle Bode plots (Figure 9b) are characterized for a single time constant for all the samples. In the case of the NC4 sample, the time constant is spread over a wide frequency range, indicating a possible porous coating structure.

The Nyquist diagrams, Figure 9c, show a similar pattern for all samples, the capacitive loop. The capacitive loop of the uncoated sample is related to the thin passive oxide film generated at the metal surface in the aqueous medium [47], [48]. We can clearly observe a larger capacitive loop for the NC4 sample compared to the untreated sample (base metal), suggesting an improvement in polarization resistance and a slower corrosion rate for the nitrided sample. For the N4-D2 and N4-D4 samples, the capacitive loops were significantly smaller than those obtained for sample NC4 and for the base metal, revealing a less noble behavior with the deposition, this result corroborates with those presented in section 3.7 and can be attributed to the defects evidenced in the coatings.

Figure 9. Bode (a, b) and Nyquist (c) diagrams for uncoated and coated samples in after 3600 s in 3.5 % NaCl solution.

The EIS diagrams of the untreated and treated samples were fitted using the Electrical Equivalent Circuit (EEC) depicted in Figure 10. Considering, the ECC is composed of the solution resistance (R_s), the capacitance of double layer (CPE_{dl}), and the resistance of charge transfer (R_{ct}). The fitted and calculated parameters R_s , CPE_{dl} , n_f , and R_{ct} are presented in Table 3. It can be seen that the CPE_{dl} values are in good agreement with those associated with the literature [49]. The NC4 sample presented the lowest values of capacitance, CPE_{dl} , which suggests the passive film formation on the surface with a lower density of defects and more uniform structure [42], on the other hand, the N4-D2 and N4-D4 samples presented higher values compared to the nitrided sample, being even higher than the one presented by the untreated sample, indicating a more porous coating that favors the penetration of the solution. The lowest values of R_{ct} were presented for the N2-D2 and N4-D4 samples, up to one order of magnitude lowest compared to the untreated sample, indicating a decrease in corrosion resistance. The NC4 sample R_{ct} value was half order of magnitude greater than the untreated sample, indicating a positive effect of nitriding on corrosion protection and evidencing that the decrease the corrosion resistance of samples with duplex treatment should be related to the deposition step.

Figure 10. Electrical equivalent circuit (EEC) used to fit the EIS results of the uncoated and coated samples.

Table 3. Results of the fitting procedure of the EIS diagrams with the EEC of the Figure 11.

Condition	Rs ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	Cc ($\text{F} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$)	Nf	Rpo ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)	CPEpl ($\text{F} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{(n-1)}$)	nf	Rpl ($\Omega \cdot \text{cm}^2$)
Untreated	30.78				$1.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.91	$4.49 \cdot 10^5$
NC4	30.20	$4.35 \cdot 10^{-5}$	1.00	$1.15 \cdot 10^5$	$1.22 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.71	$8.81 \cdot 10^5$
N4-D2	31.45				$1.02 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.72	$4.20 \cdot 10^4$
N4-D4	33.62				$9.94 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.69	$5.37 \cdot 10^4$

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the influence of plasma nitriding and duplex (nitriding followed by deposition) treatments on the corrosion resistance of UNS S32760 super duplex stainless steel was investigated. The conclusions reached are summarized below:

Analysis of the cross sections of the samples showed that the conventional nitriding treatment, under the conditions studied, results in the formation of a uniform nitride layer and that the application of deposition treatment by the cathodic cage deposition technique was effectively applied for the deposition of thin films of uniform thickness deposited on these layers.

The EDS map revealed a clear delineation between the deposited titanium nitride film and the nitride layer for sample N4-D4. The efficiency of the treatments was proven by the results obtained after Rietveld refinement of the XRD data, which proved, besides the formation of the TiN film, the formation of a nitride layer composed mainly of iron and chromium nitrides. The formation of these nitrides resulted a greater stabilization of the austenite phase by locally increasing the proportion of nickel in iron.

The results showed that the nitrided layer of the NC4 sample provides good corrosion protection to the metal substrate. In the polarization test, although the corrosion potential was lower than in the untreated sample, the corrosion current reduction evidenced a slower corrosion process and in the impedance test, all parameters indicated a nobler behavior of the NC4 sample. On the other hand, the deposition of TiN films, N4-D2 and, N4-D4 samples, decreased the UNS S32760 super duplex stainless steel corrosion resistance, it was evidenced by the presence of a coating with a more defective morphology that contributed to the change of the corrosion regime (from generalized corrosion to pitting corrosion), where the pores worked as access channels for the solution, facilitating the contact with a substrate less rich in chromium.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior (CAPES) for the financial support.

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